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Part I

Single-type model

S1 Relationships between existing models

In the appendix, we proved that one could go from the most general case to specific sub-models by incorporating additional constraints to the parameters. In this section, we illustrate how to work in the other direction — that is, to start with the most assumptions of a particular sub-model and derive its likelihood function using the same five-step procedure used to derive the general BDS model in the Main Text. In addition to illustrating the utility of our mathematical technique, by deriving the likelihoods of previously developed models, we are able to unify a diverse and, occasionally opaque, literature using a common terminology, notation, and formulation.

S1.1 Stadler 2009

Here we re-derive the likelihood given by **Equation 2** in (Stadler, 2009). Note throughout all equation, corollary, and theorem references in other publications will be placed in bold face type.

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Constant rates: $\lambda(\tau) = \lambda$, $\mu(\tau) = \mu$.
 - Birth-death model with incomplete sampling at present day: $\psi(\tau) = 0$ and $\rho_0 \leq 1$.
 - Conditioning on there being exactly N_0 lineages at the present day given the time of origin, \mathcal{S}_6 and un-ordered birth events $\mathcal{S}_8 = (N_0 - 1)!$.

- Step 2: IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda - \mu)g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda g_e(\tau)E(\tau)$$
$$g_e(\tau) = \begin{cases} \lambda g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth} \\ \rho_0 & \text{present day} \end{cases}$$

- Step 3: IVP for $E(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda + \mu)E(\tau) + \lambda E(\tau)^2 + \mu \quad \text{where } E(0) = 1 - \rho_0.$$

Given the constant rate assumption there exists a general solution for $E(\tau)$.

$$E(\tau) = \frac{\lambda + \mu + c_1 \frac{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) - (1+c_2)}{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) + (1+c_2)}}{2\lambda}$$
$$c_1 = \lambda - \mu \quad c_2 = \frac{\lambda - \mu - 2\lambda\rho_0}{\lambda - \mu}$$

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \rho_0^{N_0} \lambda^{N_0-1} \prod_{edges} \Psi(s_e, t_e).$$

- Step 5: Calculate $g_{stem}(T)$ wrt the critical time representation. Given the assumption of constant rates and no Poisson sampling the expression for $\Phi(\tau)$ simplifies to:

$$\Phi(\tau) = \frac{e^{-x(\lambda-\mu)}(\lambda-\mu)^2}{((\lambda(1-\rho_0) - \mu)e^{-x(\lambda-\mu)} + \lambda\rho_0)^2}.$$

Hence we have:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \rho_0^{N_0} \lambda^{N_0-1} \prod_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \frac{e^{-x_i(\lambda-\mu)}(\lambda-\mu)^2}{((\lambda(1-\rho_0) - \mu)e^{-x_i(\lambda-\mu)} + \lambda\rho_0)^2}.$$

- Step 6: Impose conditioning. The likelihood is conditioned on having exactly N_0 lineages at the present day (\mathcal{S}_6) and a constant $\mathcal{S}_8 = (N_0 - 1)!$ as the birth events are left un-ordered.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{S}09} = \frac{(N_0 - 1)!}{\hat{E}_{N_0}(T)} \rho_0^{N_0} \lambda^{N_0-1} \prod_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \frac{e^{-x_i(\lambda-\mu)}(\lambda-\mu)^2}{((\lambda(1-\rho_0) - \mu)e^{-x_i(\lambda-\mu)} + \lambda\rho_0)^2}. \quad (\text{S1})$$

S1.2 Stadler 2010

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Constant rates: $\lambda(\tau) = \lambda$, $\mu(\tau) = \mu$, $\psi(\tau) = \psi$.
 - No removal upon sampling, $r = 0$.
 - Multiple presented.
 - * **Equation 3 (Stadler, 2010)**: No conditioning.
 - * **Equation 4 (Stadler, 2010)**: Exactly N_0 extant sampled tips.
 - * **Corollary 3.7 (Stadler, 2010)**: At least one extant tip conditioning on the time of origin.
 - * **Equation 5 (Stadler, 2010)**: At least one extant tip conditioning on the t_{MRCA} .
 - * **Equation 6 (Stadler, 2010)**: N_0 extant tips conditioning on the time the t_{MRCA} .

- Step 2: IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda g_e(\tau)E(\tau)$$

$$g_e(s_e) = \begin{cases} \lambda g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges } e1 \text{ and } e2 \\ \psi g_e(s_e) & \text{ancestral sampling event} \\ \psi E(s_e) & \text{terminal sampling event} \\ \rho_0 & s_e = 0, \text{ edge sampled at present day} \end{cases}$$

- Step 3: IVP for $E(\tau)$. Given the constant rate assumption there exists a general solution for $E(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)E(\tau) + \lambda E(\tau)^2 + \mu \quad \text{where } E(0) = 1 - \rho_0.$$

This is a Bernoulli differential equation and has a known solution as given by Stadler (Stadler, 2010).

$$E(t) = \frac{\lambda + \mu + c_1 \frac{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) - (1+c_2)}{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) + (1+c_2)}}{2\lambda}$$

$$c_1 = \left| \sqrt{(\lambda - \mu - \psi)^2 + 4\lambda\psi} \right| \quad c_2 = \frac{\lambda - \mu - 2\lambda\rho_0 - \psi}{c_1}.$$

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\rho_0^{N_0}}_{\text{extant tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^I \lambda}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{j=1}^n \psi E(y_j)}_{\text{extinct tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{k=1}^m \psi}_{\text{ancestral samples}} \underbrace{\prod_{e \in \mathcal{T}} \Psi(s_e, t_e)}_{\text{edges}}.$$

- Step 5: Calculate $g_{stem}(T)$ wrt the critical time representation. Given the assumption of constant rates and no Poisson sampling the expression for $\Phi(\tau)$ simplifies to:

$$\Phi(\tau) = \exp \left[\int_0^\tau 2\lambda E(x) - (\lambda + \mu + \psi) dx \right].$$

Hence we have:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\Phi(T)}_{\text{root}} \underbrace{\rho_0^{N_0}}_{\text{extant tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^I \lambda \Phi(x_i)}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi}{\Phi(y_j)} E(y_j)}_{\text{extinct tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{k=1}^m \psi}_{\text{ancestral samples}}.$$

- Step 6: Impose conditioning. Imposing an arbitrary conditioning we have the following likelihood. Note that $I = N_0 + n - 1$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{S10} = \mathcal{S} \Phi(T) \rho_0^{N_0} \lambda^{N_0+n-1} \psi^{n+m} \prod_{i=1}^{N_0+n-1} \Phi(x_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{E(y_j)}{\Phi(y_j)} \quad (\text{S2})$$

- **Equation 3** (Stadler, 2010): No conditioning. $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_0 = 1$.
- **Equation 4** (Stadler, 2010): Exactly N_0 extant sampled tips. $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_6 = \frac{1}{\hat{E}_{N_0}(T)}$ where in the case of constant rates we have:

$$\hat{E}_{N_0}(T) = \hat{\phi}(T) \left(\frac{\mu}{\lambda} E(T) \right)^{N_0-1}.$$

where $\hat{\phi}(\tau)$ equals $\phi(\tau)$ where $\psi = 0$.

- **Corollary 3.7** (Stadler, 2010): At least one extant tip conditioning on the time of origin. $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_4 = \frac{1}{1 - \hat{E}(T)}$ where $\hat{E}(T)$ is given by the solution for $E(\tau)$ above given that $\psi = 0$.
- **Equation 5** (Stadler, 2010): At least one extant tip conditioning on the t_{MRCA} , $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_{5'} = \frac{\phi(x_1)}{\phi(T)(1 - \hat{E}(x_1))^2}$.
- **Equation 6** (Stadler, 2010): N_0 extant tips conditioning on the time the t_{MRCA} , $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_7 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(t_{or})} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \hat{E}_i(x_1) \hat{E}_{N_0-i}(x_1) \right)^{-1}$,

S1.3 Morlon *et al.* 2011

Here we derive **Equation 1** from (Morlon *et al.*, 2011).

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Time variable rates.
 - Birth-death only $\psi(\tau) = 0$.
 - At least one extant sample $\mathcal{S}_2 = \mathcal{S}_4$.
- Step 2: IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau))g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda(\tau)g_e(\tau)E(\tau)$$

$$g_e(s_e) = \begin{cases} \lambda_{g_{e1}(s_e)}g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges } e1 \text{ and } e2 \\ \rho_0 & s_e = 0, \text{ edge sampled at present day} \end{cases}$$

- Step 3: IVP for $E(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau))E(\tau) + \lambda(\tau)E(\tau)^2 + \mu(\tau) \quad \text{where } E(0) = 1 - \rho_0.$$

The general solution of this differential equation is given by:

$$E(\tau) = 1 - \frac{\rho_0 \exp\left[\int_0^\tau (\lambda(u) - \mu(u)) du\right]}{1 + \int_0^\tau \rho_0 \exp\left[\int_0^x (\lambda(u) - \mu(u)) du\right] dx},$$

see **Equation 2** in (Morlon *et al.*, 2011).

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\rho_0^{N_0}}_{\text{extant tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^I \lambda(x_i)}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{e \in \mathcal{J}} \Psi(s_e, t_e)}_{\text{edges}},$$

where the expression for $\Psi(s_e, t_e)$ is given by **Equation 3** in (Morlon *et al.*, 2011).

- Step 5: Calculate $g_{stem}(T)$ wrt the critical time representation. Given $\Phi(\tau) = \Psi(0, \tau)$ from **Equation 3** for in (Morlon *et al.*, 2011) we have:

$$\Phi(\tau) = \exp\left[\int_0^\tau (\lambda(\sigma) - \mu(\sigma)) d\sigma\right] \left[1 + \frac{\int_0^\tau \rho_0 \lambda(u) \exp\left[\int_0^u (\lambda(\sigma) - \mu(\sigma)) d\sigma\right] du}{1 + \rho_0}\right]^{-2}.$$

Hence we have:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\Phi(T)}_{\text{root}} \underbrace{\rho_0^{N_0}}_{\text{extant tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \lambda(x_i) \Phi(x_i)}_{\text{births}}.$$

Note $I = N_0 - 1$.

- Step 6: Impose conditioning. The likelihood given by **Equation 1** in (Morlon et al., 2011) is conditioned on the existence of at least one sampled lineage, $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_3 = \frac{1}{1-E(t_{\text{or}})}$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{M11} = \frac{\rho_0^{N_0}}{1 - E(t_{\text{or}})} \Phi(T) \prod_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \lambda(x_i) \Phi(x_i) \quad (\text{S3})$$

S1.4 Stadler et al. 2011

Here we derive the likelihoods given by **Theorem 2.6** and **2.7** in (Stadler, 2011).

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - piecewise-constant Poissonian rates. $\lambda(\tau) = \lambda_l$ and $\bar{\mu}(\tau) = \bar{\mu}_l$ if $t_l \leq \tau < t_{l+1}$ $l = 0, 2, \dots, L+1$ where $t_0 = 0$ and $t_{L+1} = T$.
 - No Poisson sampling, $\psi(\tau) = 0$.
 - Mass extinction events at times t_l $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$ as specified above.

$$\mu(\tau) = \bar{\mu} + \sum_l^L m_l \delta(\tau - t_l)$$

$$m_l = -\ln(1 - \nu_l).$$

- **Theorem 2.6** (Stadler, 2011) imposes no additional conditioning $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_0$ whereas **Theorem 2.7** (Stadler, 2011) conditions on observing at least one descendent given the time of the most recent common ancestor $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_2 = \mathcal{S}_4$.
- Step 2: IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau))g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda(\tau)g_e(\tau)E(\tau)$$

$$g_e(s_e) = \begin{cases} \lambda(s_e)g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges } e1 \text{ and } e2 \\ \rho_0 & s_e = 0, \text{ edge sampled at present day,} \end{cases}$$

where $\mu(\tau)$ is given above.

In terms of the probability flow $g_e(\tau) = g_e(s_e)\Psi(s_e, \tau)$, where:

$$\Psi(s_e, \tau) = \exp \left[\int_{s_e}^{\tau} 2\lambda(x)E(x) - (\lambda(x) + \mu(x)) dx \right].$$

Here $\mu(\tau)$ includes the mass extinction events.

- Step 3: IVP for $E(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau))E(\tau) + \lambda(\tau)E(\tau)^2 + \mu(\tau)$$

$$E(0) = 1 - \rho_0.$$

Given the piecewise constant nature there is a known general solution. Let $E(\tau) = E_l(\tau)$ where $t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$. Then define $E_{l-1}(t_l^-)$ as the solution up to but not including the mass extinction event at time t_l we have:

$$E_l(t_l) = E_{l-1}(t_l) = (1 - \nu_l)E_{l-1}(t_l^-) + \nu_l,$$

where $E_l(\tau)$ is given by a solution similar to that in Equation (A1).

$$E_l(\tau) = \frac{\lambda_l + \bar{\mu}_l}{2\lambda_l} + \frac{c_1}{2\lambda_l} \frac{e^{-c_1\tau}(1 - c_2) - (1 + c_2)}{e^{-c_1\tau}(1 - c_2) + (1 + c_2)}$$

$$c_1 = \left| \sqrt{(\lambda_l - \bar{\mu}_l)^2} \right| \quad c_2 = -\frac{\lambda_l - \bar{\mu}_l - 2\lambda_l(1 - E_l(t_l))}{c_1},$$

where $E_0(t_0) = 1 - \rho_0$.

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$. The expression for $g_{stem}(T)$ is given by:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\rho_0^{N_0}}_{\text{extant tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^I \lambda(x_i)}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{e \in \mathcal{T}} \Psi(s_e, t_e)}_{\text{edges}},$$

where $\lambda(\tau)$ and $\Psi(s_e, \tau)$ are specified above.

- Step 5: The critical time representation. We once again define the sub-flow $\Phi_l(\tau)$ where $t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_l(\tau) &= \exp \left[\int_{t_l}^{\tau} 2\lambda(x)E(x) - (\lambda(x) + \bar{\mu}(x) + m_l\delta(x - t_l)) dx \right] \\ &= \exp \left[\int_{t_l}^{\tau} 2\lambda(x)E(x) - (\lambda(x) + \bar{\mu}(x)) dx \right] (1 - \nu_l) \\ &= \bar{\Phi}_l(\tau) (1 - \nu_l). \end{aligned}$$

Note $\nu_0 = 0$. The complete flow is, as given by Equation (A3).

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(\tau) &= \bar{\Phi}_{L_\tau}(\tau) \prod_{l=1}^{L_\tau} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \\ \Phi(t_k) &= \underbrace{\bar{\Phi}_k(t_k)}_1 \prod_{l=1}^k \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) = \prod_{l=1}^k \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l), \end{aligned}$$

where L_τ is once again the largest index l such that $t_l < \tau$.

The critical time representation of g_{stem} then is:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \right].$$

Defining α_l as the number of observed birth events $\geq t_l$ we can rewrite the product:

$$\begin{aligned}\prod_{i=1}^I \prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) &= \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) \right)^{\alpha_l} \\ \prod_{i=1}^I \prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} (1 - \nu_l) &= \prod_{l=1}^L (1 - \nu_l)^{\alpha_l}\end{aligned}$$

Hence we have:

$$\begin{aligned}g_{stem}(T) &= \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \right)^{\alpha_l + 1} \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \right] \\ &= \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \right)^{n_l} \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \right],\end{aligned}$$

where n_l is the number of lineages in the observed phylogeny at time t_l then $n_l = \alpha_l + 1$.

- Step 6: Likelihood conditioning.

For **Theorem 2.6** (Stadler, 2011) the likelihood is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{S11} = \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \right)^{n_l} \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \right]$$

For **Theorem 2.7** (Stadler, 2011) the likelihood is given by:

$$\mathcal{L}_{S11} = \frac{\rho_0^{N_0}}{(1 - E(x_1))^2} \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_1}}(x_1) \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \nu_l) \right)^{n_l} \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \right]$$

S1.5 Stadler *et al.* 2012

Here we derive **Equation 1** in (Stadler *et al.*, 2012).

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Constant birth, death, and sampling rates.
 - No present day sampling. All lineages removed upon sampling $r = 1$.
 - No conditioning.
- Step 2: IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} &= -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda g_e(\tau)E(\tau) \\ g_e(s_e) &= \begin{cases} \lambda(s_e)g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges e1 and e2} \\ \psi(s_e) & \text{terminal sampling event} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

- Step 3: IVP for $E(\tau)$.

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)E(\tau) + \lambda E(\tau)^2 + \mu \quad \text{where } E(0) = 0.$$

The solution to this differential equation is given by:

$$E(t) = \frac{\lambda + \mu + c_1 \frac{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) - (1+c_2)}{\exp[-c_1 t](1-c_2) + (1+c_2)}}{2\lambda}$$

$$c_1 = \left| \sqrt{(\lambda - \mu - \psi)^2 + 4\lambda\psi} \right| \quad c_2 = \frac{\lambda - \mu - \psi}{c_1}.$$

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^I \lambda}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{j=1}^n \psi}_{\text{extinct tips}} \underbrace{\prod_{e \in \mathcal{J}} \Psi(s_e, t_e)}_{\text{edges}}$$

$$= \lambda^{n-1} \psi^n \prod_{e \in \mathcal{J}} \Psi(s_e, t_e),$$

where $I = n - 1$.

- Step 5: Critical time representation. Given the assumption of constant rates and no Poisson sampling the expression for $\Phi(t)$ simplifies to:

$$\Phi(\tau) = \exp \left[\int_0^\tau 2\lambda E(x) - (\lambda + \mu + \psi) dx \right].$$

Hence we have:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \underbrace{\Phi(T)}_{\text{root}} \lambda^{n-1} \psi^n \underbrace{\prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \Phi(x_i)}_{\text{births}} \underbrace{\prod_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\Phi(y_j)}}_{\text{extinct tips}}$$

- Step 6: Impose conditioning $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_0$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{S12} = \lambda^{n-1} \psi^n \Phi(T) \prod_{i=1}^{n-1} \Phi(x_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\Phi(y_j)} \quad (\text{S4})$$

S1.6 Stadler *et al.* 2013 and Gavryushkina *et al.* 2014

Here we derive the tree likelihood given by **Theorem 1** in (Stadler and Bonhoeffer, 2013) and due to their shared the likelihood given by **Equation 4** in (Gavryushkina *et al.*, 2014).

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Piecewise constant Poissonian birth, death, and sampling rates.
 - * define transition times $0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_{L+1} = T$.

- * $\lambda(\tau) = \lambda_l t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$.
- * $\mu(\tau) = \mu_l t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$.
- * $\bar{\psi}(\tau) = \bar{\psi}_l t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$.
- Fossils/Ancestral sampling:
 - * (Stadler and Bonhoeffer, 2013): No fossils $r = 1$.
 - * (Gavryushkina et al., 2014): piecewise-constant rate $r(\tau) = r_l t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$.
- Concerted sampling attempts at each internal transition time t_l where $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$.
 - * The probability of a lineage being sampled during the CSA at time t_l is ρ_l .
 - * The resulting total sampling rate is given by:

$$\psi(\tau) = \bar{\psi}(\tau) + \sum_{l=1}^L w_l \delta(\tau - t_l)$$

$$w_l = -\ln(1 - \rho_l).$$

- Conditioning:
 - * Stadler et al. (Stadler and Bonhoeffer, 2013)—At least one sampled lineage, $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_2$.
 - * Gavryushkina et al. (Gavryushkina et al., 2014)— At least one sample (\mathcal{S}_2) and a constant giving the number of un-oriented phylogenies $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S}_8$.
- Step 2: Derive IVP for $g_e(\tau)$. As in section A2.3 we have:

$$\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau) + \psi(\tau))g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda(\tau)g_e(\tau)E(\tau)$$

$$g_e(s_e) = \begin{cases} \lambda(s_e)g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges e1 and e2} \\ (1 - r(s_e))\bar{\psi}(s_e)g_{e1}(s_e) & \text{Poisson ancestral sampling event} \\ \bar{\psi}(s_e)r(s_e) + \bar{\psi}(s_e)(1 - r(s_e))E(s_e) & \text{Poisson terminal sampling event} \\ (1 - r(t_l))\rho_l g_{e1}(t_l) & \text{ancestral sample at } t_l \\ \rho_l r(t_l) + \rho_l(1 - r(t_l))E(t_l) & \text{terminal sample at } t_l \\ \rho_0 & s_e = 0, \text{ edge sampled at present day} \end{cases}$$

- Step 3: Derive IVP for $E(\tau)$. The IVP for $E(\tau)$ follows from Equation (8).

$$\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\lambda(\tau) + \mu(\tau) + \psi(\tau))E(\tau) + \lambda(\tau)E(\tau)^2 + \mu(\tau)$$

$$E(0) = 1 - \rho_0.$$

Given the piecewise constant nature there is a known general solution. Let $E(\tau) = E_l(\tau)$ where $t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$. Then define $E_{l-1}(t_l^-)$ as the solution up to but not including the CSA at time t_l we have:

$$E_l(t_l) = E_{l-1}(t_l) = (1 - \rho_l)E_{l-1}(t_l^-),$$

where $E_l(\tau)$ is given by a solution similar to that in Equation (A1).

$$E_l(\tau) = \frac{\lambda_l + \mu_l + \bar{\psi}_l}{2\lambda_l} + \frac{c_1 e^{-c_1 \tau} (1 - c_2) - (1 + c_2)}{2\lambda_l e^{-c_1 \tau} (1 - c_2) + (1 + c_2)}$$

$$c_1 = \left| \sqrt{(\lambda_l - \mu_l - \bar{\psi}_l)^2 + 4\lambda_l + \bar{\psi}_l} \right| \quad c_2 = -\frac{\lambda_l - \mu_l - 2\lambda_l(1 - E_l(t_l)) - \bar{\psi}_l}{c_1},$$

where $E_0(t_0) = 1 - \rho_0$.

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$. As in section A2.3 the edge representation of g_{stem} is given by:

$$g_{stem}(T) = \rho_0^{N_0} \prod_{i=1}^L \lambda(x_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \psi(y_j) [(1 - r(y_j))E(y_j) + r(y_j)] \prod_{k=1}^m \psi(z_k)(1 - r(y_j))$$

$$\times \prod_{l=1}^L \rho_l [(1 - r_l)E(t_l) + r_l]^{N_l} \prod_{l=1}^L [\rho_l(1 - r_l)]^{M_l} \prod_{edges} \Psi(s_e, t_e),$$

where $\Psi(s_e, t_e)$ is given by Equation (6).

- Step 5: Critical time representation. We once again define the sub-flow $\Phi_l(\tau)$ where $t_l < \tau \leq t_{l+1}$:

$$\Phi_l(\tau) = \exp \left[\int_{t_l}^{\tau} 2\lambda(x)E(x) - \left(\lambda(x) + \mu(x) + \bar{\psi}(x) + w_l \delta(x - t_l) \right) dx \right]$$

$$= \exp \left[\int_{t_l}^{\tau} 2\lambda(x)E(x) - \left(\lambda(x) + \mu(x) + \bar{\psi}(s) \right) dx \right] (1 - \rho_l)$$

$$= \bar{\Phi}_l(\tau) (1 - \rho_l).$$

The complete flow is, as given by Equation (A3).

$$\Phi(\tau) = \bar{\Phi}_{L_\tau}(\tau) \prod_{l=1}^{L_\tau} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l)$$

$$\Phi(t_k) = \underbrace{\bar{\Phi}_k(t_k)}_1 \prod_{l=1}^k \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l) = \prod_{l=1}^k \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l),$$

where L_τ is once again the largest index l such that $t_l < \tau$. The critical time representation of g_{stem} from the previous stem gives the following.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l) \prod_{i=1}^I \lambda(x_i) \bar{\Phi}_{L_{x_i}}(x_i) \prod_{i=1}^I \left[\prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l) \right]$$

$$\times \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi(y_j)}{\bar{\Phi}_{L_{y_j}}(y_j)} [(1 - r(y_j))E(y_j) + r(y_j)] \prod_{j=1}^n \left[\prod_{l=1}^{L_{y_j}} \frac{1}{\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) (1 - \rho_l)} \right] \prod_{k=1}^m \psi(z_k) (1 - r(z_k))$$

$$\times \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\bar{\Phi}_l(t_l)} [(1 - r_l)E(t_l) + r_l] \right)^{N_l} \prod_{l=1}^L \left[\prod_{j=1}^l \frac{1}{(1 - \rho_j) \bar{\Phi}_{j-1}(t_j)} \right]^{N_l} \prod_{l=1}^L [\rho_l(1 - r_l)]^{M_l}.$$

We can then simplify the likelihood using the relationships similar to those given by Equation (A4).

$$\begin{aligned}
\prod_{i=1}^I \prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} \bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l) &= \prod_{l=1}^L [\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)]^{\alpha_l} \\
\prod_{j=1}^n \prod_{l=1}^{L_{y_j}} \frac{1}{\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)} &= \prod_{l=1}^L [\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)]^{-\sigma_l} . \\
\prod_{i=1}^I \prod_{l=1}^{L_{x_i}} (1 - \rho_l) &= \prod_{l=1}^L (1 - \rho_l)^{\alpha_l} \\
\prod_{j=1}^n \prod_{l=1}^{L_{y_j}} \frac{1}{(1 - \rho_l)} &= \prod_{l=1}^L (1 - \rho_l)^{-\sigma_l} \\
\prod_{l=1}^L \left[\prod_{j=1}^l \frac{1}{(1 - \rho_j)^{N_l}} \right] &= \prod_{l=1}^L \frac{1}{(1 - \rho_l)^{\beta_l}} ,
\end{aligned}$$

where α_l is the number of birth events before time t_l and σ_l is the number of Poisson sampling events before time t_l and β_l is the number of lineages sampled during the CSAs up to and including at time t_l .

The resulting simplified likelihood is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{stem}(T) &= \rho_0^{N_0} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L [\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)(1 - \rho_l)]^{\alpha_l + 1 - \sigma_l - \beta_l} \\
&\times \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi(y_j)}{\bar{\Phi}_{L_{y_j}}(y_j)} [(1 - r(y_j))E(y_j) + r(y_j)] \prod_{k=1}^m \psi(z_k)(1 - r(z_k)) \\
&\times \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\bar{\Phi}_l(t_l)} [(1 - r_l)E(t_l) + r_l] \right)^{N_l} \prod_{l=1}^L [\rho_l(1 - r_l)]^{M_l} .
\end{aligned}$$

• Step 6: Conditioned likelihood.

- Stadler et al. (Stadler and Bonhoeffer, 2013) conditions on observing at least one sample. In addition the likelihood given by Stadler et al. assumes that all lineages are removed upon sampling $r_l = 1$ an assumption we will apply now. The likelihoods can be simplified by letting $n_l = \alpha_l + 1 - \sigma_l - \beta_l$ be the number of lineages that are alive immediately following the concerted sampling attempt at time t_l

$$\mathcal{L}_{S13} = \frac{\rho_0^{N_0}}{1 - E(T)} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L [\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)(1 - \rho_l)]^{n_l} \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi(y_j)}{\bar{\Phi}_{L_{y_j}}(y_j)} \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\bar{\Phi}_l(t_l)} \right)^{N_l} . \quad (S5)$$

- Gavryushkina et al. (Gavryushkina et al., 2014) also condition on observing at least one lineage

as well as multiply by a constant giving the number of un-oriented trees.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}_{G14} = & \mathcal{S}_8 \frac{\rho_0^{N_0}}{1 - E(T)} \bar{\Phi}_L(T) \prod_{l=1}^L \left[\bar{\Phi}_{l-1}(t_l)(1 - \rho_l) \right]^{n_l} \\
& \times \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi(y_j)}{\bar{\Phi}_{L y_j}(y_j)} [(1 - r(y_j))E(y_j) + r(y_j)] \prod_{k=1}^m \psi(z_k)(1 - r(z_k)) \\
& \times \prod_{l=1}^L \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\bar{\Phi}_l(t_l)} [(1 - r_l)E(t_l) + r_l] \right)^{N_l} \prod_{l=1}^L [\rho_l(1 - r_l)]^{M_l}
\end{aligned} \tag{S6}$$

S1.7 Heath *et al.* 2014

- Step 1: Specify the model.
 - Constant rates: $\lambda(\tau) = \lambda$, $\mu(\tau) = \mu$, $\psi(\tau) = \psi$.
 - * Here ψ denotes the sampling rate of fossils.
 - Birth-death model with fossils, $r = 0$.
 - Conditioned on observing ≥ 1 sample given $t_{MRC A}$ (\mathcal{S}_3) and enumerated over all possible attachments of fossils (terminal sampling events before the present day (\mathcal{S}_8)).
- Step 2: Derive IVP for $g_e(\tau)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dg_e(\tau)}{d\tau} &= -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)g_e(\tau) + 2\lambda g_e(\tau)E(\tau) \\
g_e(s_e) &= \begin{cases} \lambda g_{e1}(s_e)g_{e2}(s_e) & \text{birth event giving rise to edges } e1 \text{ and } e2 \\ \psi g_{e1}(s_e) & \text{ancestral sampling event} \\ \psi E(s_e) & \text{terminal sampling event} \\ \rho_0 & s_e = 0, \text{ edge sampled at present day} \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

- Step 3: Derive IVP for $E(\tau)$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dE(\tau)}{d\tau} &= -(\lambda + \mu + \psi)E(\tau) + \lambda E(\tau)^2 + \mu \\
E(0) &= 1 - \rho_0.
\end{aligned}$$

This has the same general solution as given above in section S1.2.

- Step 4: Derive $g_{stem}(T)$.

$$g_{stem}(T) = (\rho_0)^{N_0} \prod_{i=1}^I \lambda \prod_{j=1}^n \psi E(y_j) \prod_{k=1}^m \psi \prod_{edges} \Psi(s_e, t_e).$$

- Step 5: Critical time representation.

$$g_{stem}(T) = \Phi(T) (\rho_0)^{N_0} \prod_{i=1}^I \lambda \Phi(x_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{\psi}{\bar{\Phi}(y_j)} E(y_j) \prod_{k=1}^m \psi.$$

- Step 6: Conditioned likelihood. Conditioning on the probability that both daughter clades of the MRCA have at least one sampled extant descendant. S'_5 . The general solution to $\hat{E}(\tau)$ is known as given by the solution to $E(\tau)$ in section S1.1. Conditioning on all the possible attachments of the fossils (terminal samples before the present day). This requires multiplication by a constant S_8 . Let $\gamma(\tau)$ be the number of lineages alive at time τ . The the resulting number of fossil trees is.

$$S = \prod_{i=1}^n 2\gamma(y_j) \prod_{k=1}^m \gamma(z_k). \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{H14} = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{(1 - \hat{E}(x_1))^2} (\rho_0)^{N_0} \prod_{i=1}^I \lambda \Phi(x_i) \prod_{j=1}^n \frac{2\gamma(y_j)\psi}{\Phi(y_j)} E(y_j) \prod_{k=1}^m \gamma(z_k)\psi \quad (\text{S8})$$

S2 Tables

General Birth-Death-Sampling Model Notation

Variable	Definition
$\lambda(\tau)$	The rate at which lineages speciate at time τ^a . $\lambda : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$
$\mu(\tau)$	The rate at which lineages go extinct at time τ . $\mu : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$
$\psi(\tau)$	The rate at which lineages are sampled at time τ . $\psi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$
$r(\tau)$	The probability that sampling is associated with host recovery/viral extinction at time τ . $r : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$
ρ_0	The probability of sampling a lineage alive at the present day. $\rho_0 : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, 1]$
T	The time of origin of the phylogeny/epidemic.
\vec{x}	The vector of I branching times. $\vec{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_I\}^d$
\vec{y}	The vector of n internal (Poisson) sampling times without sampled descendants (terminal nodes). $\vec{y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_j, \dots, y_n\}$
\vec{z}	The vector of m internal (Poisson) sampling times of lineages with sampled descendants (sampled ancestors). $\vec{z} = \{z_1, z_2, \dots, z_k, \dots, z_m\}$
N_0	The number of lineage sampled at the present day.
$g_e(\tau)$	The likelihood density of observing a given phylogeny by the present day descending from a single edge e alive at age τ^e .
$E(\tau)$	The probability that a lineage alive at time τ leaves no sampled descendants in the phylogeny ^f .
\mathcal{S}	The conditioning of the phylogeny.
$\Theta_{\text{BDS}} = \{\lambda(\tau), \mu(\tau), \psi(\tau), r(\tau), T, \rho_0\}$	
CSA ^b , mass extinctions, and piecewise constant models	
L	The total number of past concerted sampling events.
L_t	The index of the time t_l at or after time t , i.e. the largest index such that $t_l \leq \tau$.
\vec{t}	Vector of times of CSAs in order of most recent to oldest $t_1 < t_2 < \dots < t_L$. $\vec{t} = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_l, \dots, t_L\}^c$
$\vec{\rho}$	Vector of sampling probabilities of lineages sampled during each CSA. $\rho_l : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow (0, 1]$. $\vec{\rho} = \{\rho_0, \rho_1, \dots, \rho_l, \dots, \rho_L\}$
\vec{r}	The probability that a lineage that is sampled during each CSA is removed upon sampling. $r_l : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, 1]$. $\vec{r} = \{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_l, \dots, r_L\}$
N_l	The number of tips sampled during the CSA at time t_l .
M_l	The number of ancestral samples during the CSA at time t_l .
n_l	The number of lineages that cross time t_l .
α_l	The number of observed birth events prior to time t_l ($x_i > t_l$).
$\sigma_l(\beta_l)$	The number of Poissonian (concerted) sampled lineages prior to or at time $\tau \geq t_l$.
$\Theta_{\text{CSA}} = \{\lambda(\tau), \mu(\tau), \psi(\tau), r(\tau), T, \vec{t}, \vec{\rho}, \vec{r}\}$	

Table S1: **model notation.**

^aThroughout τ is measured in units of time before the present day ($\tau = 0$).

^b CSA: Concerted Sampling Attempt.

^c When used t_0 indicates the present day and $t_{L+1} = T$.

^d When used x_1 indicates the time of the most recent common ancestor τ_{MRCA}

^e The edge e spans time τ , $s_e \geq \tau \geq t_e$

^f $\hat{E}(\tau)$ is the special case where $\psi(\tau) = 0$

Model	$\lambda(\tau), \mu(\tau), \psi(\tau)$	$r(\tau)$	ρ_0	ρ_l	r_l	ν_l	\mathcal{S}	Section
Stadler 2009	constant, $\psi = 0$	NA	> 0	0	NA	0	$\mathcal{S}_6 \mathcal{S}_8$	S1.1
Stadler 2010	constant	0	> 0	0	NA	0	multiple	S1.2
Morlon et al. 2011	$\psi = 0$	NA	> 0	0	NA	0	$\mathcal{S}_1 = \mathcal{S}_2$	S1.3
Stadler 2011	piecewise, $\psi = 0$	NA	> 0	0	NA	≥ 0	$\mathcal{S}_3 = \mathcal{S}_5$	S1.4
Stadler et al. 2012	constant	1	0	0	NA	0	\mathcal{S}_1	S1.5
Stadler and Bonhoeffer 2013	piecewise	1	> 0	≥ 0	1	0	\mathcal{S}_1	S1.6
Gavryushkina et al. 2014	piecewise	piecewise	> 0	≥ 0	≥ 0	0	$\mathcal{S}_1 \times \mathcal{S}_7$	S1.6
Kühnert et al. 2014	stochastic SIR	constant	0	0	NA	0	? ^a	
Heath et al. 2014	constant	0	> 0	0	NA	0	\mathcal{S}_6	S1.7

Table S2: **Relationship of single-type sub-models to the general BDS model.**

^a No specific conditioning mentioned.

Condition	Description	Examples
$\mathcal{S}_0 = 1$	No conditioning	Eq.3 (Stadler, 2010), Eq.1 (Stadler et al., 2012) & Thrm. 2.6 (Stadler, 2011)
$\mathcal{S}_1 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(T)}$	Likelihood given the t_{MRCA} rather than on the time of origin.	
$\mathcal{S}_2 = \frac{1}{1-\hat{E}(T)}$	At least one sampled descendent either at or before the present day (given T).	Eq.2 Morlon et al. (2011), Thrm.1 Stadler and Bonhoeffer (2013) (Heath et al., 2014)
$\mathcal{S}_3 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(T)(1-\hat{E}(x_1))^2}$	At least one sampled descendent at or before the present day given $\tau_{\text{MRCA}} = x_1$	
$\mathcal{S}_4 = \frac{1}{1-\hat{E}(T)}$	At least one <i>extant</i> sampled lineage (given T).	Cor.3.7 (Stadler, 2010) & Thrm.2.7 (Stadler, 2011)
$\mathcal{S}_5 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(T)2(1-\hat{E}(x_1))(1-\hat{E}(x_1))}$	At least one <i>extant</i> sampled lineage given $\tau_{\text{MRCA}} = x_1$	
$\mathcal{S}'_5 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(T)(1-\hat{E}(x_1))^2}$	Both daughters of MRCA have at least one <i>extant</i> sampled lineage	Eq. 5 Stadler (2010)
$\mathcal{S}_6 = \frac{1}{\hat{E}_{N_0}(T)}$	Exactly N_0 <i>extant</i> sampled lineages (given T).	Eq.2 Stadler (2009), Eq.4 (Stadler, 2010) & Cor.3.6 Stadler (2010)
$\mathcal{S}_7 = \frac{\Phi(x_1)}{\Phi(t_{\text{or}})} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_0-1} \hat{E}_i(x_1) \hat{E}_{N_0-i}(x_1) \right)^{-1}$	Exactly N_0 <i>extant</i> sampled lineages given t_{MRCA} .	Eq.6 Stadler (2010)
$\mathcal{S}_8 = \text{constant}$	Multiply by a constant	Stadler (2009) & Gavryushkina et al. (2014) ^a & Heath et al. (2014)

Table S3: **Alternative conditioning of tree likelihood.**

^a See Gavryushkina et al. (2013) for algorithms for enumerating trees.

Part II

The multi-type model

S3 The multi-type diversification model

Here we consider the diversification of lineages of A discrete types. Lineages of type $a \in \{1, 2, \dots, A\}$ speciate/give birth to lineages of type $b \in \{1, 2, \dots, A\}$ at the time-variable rate $\lambda_{a,b}(\tau)$ at time τ before the present day. As above we will use τ to denote time moving backward from the present day ($\tau = 0$) to the origin of the phylogeny $\tau = T$. When $a = b$ speciation occurs without cladogenetic change, when $a \neq b$ speciation is coincident with state change. In addition to the lineages changing state at birth events, lineages can mutate anagenetically from state a to state b at rate $\gamma_{a,b}(\tau)$. Lineages of type a alive at time τ , go extinct/die at rate $\mu_a(\tau)$. For $\tau > 0$ lineages are sampled at rate $\psi_a(\tau)$. Upon sampling a lineage may be removed from the population (e.g., sampling is coincident with treatment) with the state-dependent probability $r_a(\tau)$. Finally, all lineages alive at the present day are sampled with a state-dependent probability ρ_a . Model notation is summarized in Table S4.

As with the single-type model, the result of the multi-type diversification process is a *full* and a *sampled* tree. Now however the tree is characterized by its topology \mathcal{T} and the *colouring* of the tree \mathcal{C} denoting the states of each lineage through time. Below we first derive an expression for the likelihood of a given coloured tree, $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{C} | \Theta_{MBDS})$. However, as plausibly attainable data consists of knowledge at only some or all the sampled ancestral nodes and/or tips, we must then integrate the likelihood $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{C} | \Theta_{MBDS})$ over all possible tree colourings consistent with the observed data.

S3.1 Derivation of $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{C} | \Theta_{MBDS})$

We derive the likelihood using the steps used above for the single-type birth death sampling model. As with the single-type model for the likelihood calculation we begin by representing the phylogeny as a series of edges. However, as we are now referring to the coloured phylogeny we consider the set of all coloured edges, with each edge being a segment of the phylogeny that is all of one colour beginning and ending at birth, sampling, or mutation events. Specifically, moving backward in time towards the tree origin let edge e start at time s_e before the present at a birth event, sampling (ancestral or tip), or mutation event, and continue toward the tree origin until time τ_e ending at either a birth event, ancestral sampling event, mutation event or at the tree origin.

As with the single-type model the tree likelihood depends on two different functions. First, $g_{e,a}(\tau)$ is the probability that an edge e with state a alive at time τ (hence $t_e > \tau > s_e$) gives rise to the subsequently observed phylogeny between τ and the present day. Second, $E_a(\tau)$ is the probability a lineage of type a alive at time τ has no sampled descendants between τ and the present day. We begin below by first deriving the initial value problems for these two functions.

Step 1: Derive the Initial Value Problem for $g_{e,a}(\tau)$.

To simplify the notation we define the total birth and mutation rates of a given type $\Lambda_a = \sum_b \lambda_{a,b}$ and $\Gamma_a = \sum_b \gamma_{a,b}$ and the relative probability a birth or mutation event was of a given type, $p_{\lambda_{a,b}} = \frac{\lambda_{a,b}}{\Lambda_a}$ and $p_{\gamma_{a,b}} = \frac{\gamma_{a,b}}{\Gamma_a}$. For some small amount of time $\Delta\tau$ the recursion equation for $g_{e,a}(\tau)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{e,a}(\tau + \Delta\tau) \approx & \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{No Event}} g_{e,a}(\tau) \\
& + \underbrace{((\Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau)) \times \sum_b^A p_{\lambda_{a,b}} \iota_{a,b} g_{e,a}(\tau) E_b(\tau)}_{\text{Birth Events}} \\
& + \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(\mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{Death Event}} \times 0 \\
& + \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(\psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{Sampling Event}} \times 0 \\
& + \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(\Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{Mutation Events}} \times 0 + \mathcal{O}(\Delta\tau^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{S9}$$

where $\iota_{a,b}$ is an indicator variable that has value 2 when $a = b$ and 1 otherwise. This recursion equation uses the fact that edges are all in state with mutation events resulting in the end of an edge and the origin of a daughter edge with a different state. This is reflected by the initial conditions of $g_{e,a}(\tau)$ as given below in equation (S11).

As above we can then use the definition of a derivative to obtain the corresponding differential equation

$$\frac{dg_{e,a}(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\Lambda_a + \mu_a + \psi_a + \Gamma_a) g_{e,a}(\tau) + \sum_b \iota_{a,b} \lambda_{a,b} g_{e,a}(\tau) E_b(\tau) \tag{S10}$$

The initial conditions for $g_{e,a}$ at the start of the edge, time s_e , depend on the event that occurs in the sampled tree at that time. Specifically there are five types of events in the observed tree. 1) *Observed birth events* where a lineage of type a speciates producing a new lineage of type b . 2) *Ancestral sampling events* where a lineage of type a is sampled, is not removed from the population, and then has subsequently observed descendants. 3) *Terminal sampling events* where a lineage of type a is sampled and then either is immediately removed from the population or remains in the population but has no sampled descendants. 4) *Transition events* where a lineage of type a transitions to a lineage of type b . There are two possible ways a transition event can occur. First, a lineage can switch states due to anagenetic *mutation event* or second an apparent transition can arise due to a birth event with cladogenetic state change followed by subsequent extinction of the parental lineage. We refer to this second form of transition event as a *hidden birth event*.

$$g_{e,a}(s_e) = \begin{cases} \lambda_{a,b}(s_e) g_{e_1,a}(s_e) g_{e_2,b}(s_e) & \text{birth event } a \rightarrow a + b \\ (1 - r_a(s_e)) \psi_a(s_e) g_{e_1,a}(s_e) & \text{ancestral sampling event} \\ r_a(s_e) \psi_a(s_e) + (1 - r_a(s_e)) \psi_a(s_e) E_a(s_e) & \text{terminal sampling event} \\ (\gamma_{a,b}(s_e) + \lambda_{a,b} E_a) g_{e_1,b}(s_e) & \text{mutation/hidden birth event } a \rightarrow b \\ \rho_a & \text{sampled at present day} \end{cases} \tag{S11}$$

Importantly, as the ODES in equation (S10) are linear the corresponding IVP has the following general

solution given the initial conditions above.

$$g_{e,a}(\tau) = g_{e,a}(s_e)\Psi_a(s_e, \tau), \quad \text{where} \quad (S12)$$

$$\Psi_a(s_e, \tau) = \exp \left[\int_{s_e}^{\tau} -(\Lambda_a(x) + \mu_a(x) + \psi_a(x) + \Gamma_a(x)) + \sum_b \iota_{a,b} \lambda_{a,b}(x) E_b(x) dx \right].$$

The IVP for the function $E_a(\tau)$ can be derived in an analogous manner.

Step 2: Derive the Initial Value Problem for $E_a(\tau)$ Once again we begin by deriving a recursion equation for the change in $E_a(\tau)$ over from time τ to $\tau + \Delta\tau$.

$$E_a(\tau + \Delta\tau) \approx \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{No Event}} E_a(\tau)$$

$$+ \underbrace{((\Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau)) \times \sum_b^A p_{\lambda_{a,b}} E_a(\tau) E_b(\tau)}_{\text{Birth Events}}$$

$$+ \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(\mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{Death Event}} \times 1 \quad (S13)$$

$$+ \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(\psi_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \Gamma_a \Delta\tau))}_{\text{Sampling Event}} \times 0$$

$$+ \underbrace{((1 - \Lambda_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \mu_a \Delta\tau)(1 - \psi_a \Delta\tau)(\Gamma_a \Delta\tau)) \times \sum_b p_{\gamma_{a,b}} E_b(\tau)}_{\text{Mutation Events}} + \mathcal{O}(\Delta\tau^2).$$

Using the definition of a derivative we have:

$$\frac{dE_a(\tau)}{d\tau} = -(\Lambda_a + \mu_a + \psi_a + \Gamma_a) E_a(\tau) + \sum_b \lambda_{a,b} E_a(\tau) E_b(\tau) + \mu_a + \sum_b \gamma_{a,b} E_b(\tau), \quad (S14)$$

with initial conditions given at the present day by:

$$E_a(0) = 1 - \rho_a \quad (S15)$$

Step 3: Derive Expression for $g_{stem}(T)$ As in equation (9) for the single-type model, the tree likelihood is given by the value of the function g of the stem edge evaluated at the time of the origin of the phylogeny, T . From the solution to the initial value problem given by equation (S12) and the initial conditions (S11) we can write $g_{stem}(T)$ as a product over the events in the tree and all the probability flow Ψ of the edges in-between. To do so let $\vec{x}_{a,b}$ be a vector of length $I_{a,b}$, giving the time before the present day of all the observed birth events where lineages of type a give rise to lineages of type b . Let \vec{y}_a be a vector of length J_a giving the sampling time of tips of type a and \vec{z}_a a vector of length K_a the sampling type of sampled ancestors of type a . Finally let $\vec{v}_{a,b}$ be the time of observed transition events where a edge of type a transitions becomes an edge of type b . Once again, transition events can arise due to both direct mutation and hidden birth events. The resulting expression for the likelihood $g_{stem}(T)$ is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{stem}(T) = & \prod_{a=1}^A \left[\underbrace{\rho_a^{N_a}}_{\text{present day sampling}} \times \underbrace{\prod_{b=1}^A \prod_{i=1}^{I_{a,b}} \lambda_{a,b}(x_{a,b,i})}_{\text{birth events}} \right. \\
& \times \underbrace{\prod_{j=1}^{J_a} \psi_a(y_{a,j}) (1 - r_a(y_{a,j})) E_a(y_{a,j}) + \psi_a(y_{a,j}) r_a(y_{a,j})}_{\text{terminal samples}} \times \underbrace{\prod_{k=1}^{K_a} \psi_a(z_{a,k}) (1 - r_a(z_{a,k}))}_{\text{ancestral samples}} \\
& \left. \times \underbrace{\prod_{l=1}^{L_{a,b}} [\gamma_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l}) + \lambda_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l}) E_a(w_{a,b,l})]}_{\text{transitions}} \prod \Psi_a(s_e, \tau_e) \right] \text{ edges of type } a
\end{aligned} \tag{S16}$$

Step 4: Rewrite $g_{stem}(T)$ in Terms of Critical Times

Rather than enumerate Ψ over the edges of the phylogeny we can rewrite equation (S16) in terms of only the critical times $\vec{x}, \vec{y}, \vec{z}, \vec{w}$. Written in this form the likelihood also depends on c^* the colour of the phylogeny at the origin. To do so we define $\Phi_a(\tau) = \Psi_a(0, \tau)$ and rewrite the probability flow $\Psi_a(s_e, \tau)$ as a ratio:

$$\Psi_a(s_e, \tau) = \frac{\Phi_a(\tau)}{\Phi_a(s_e)} \tag{S17}$$

Substitution into equation (S16).

$$\begin{aligned}
g_{stem, c^*}(T) = & \underbrace{\left[\prod_{a=1}^A \rho_a^{N_a} \right]}_{\text{present day sampling}} \times \underbrace{[\Phi_{c^*}(T)]}_{\text{stem}} \times \underbrace{\left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{b=1}^A \prod_{i=1}^{I_{a,b}} \lambda_{a,b}(x_{a,b,i}) \frac{\Phi_a(x_{a,b,i}) \Phi_b(x_{a,b,i})}{\Phi_a(x_{a,b,i})} \right]}_{\text{birth events}} \\
& \times \underbrace{\left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{j=1}^{J_a} [\psi_a(y_{a,j}) (1 - r_a(y_{a,j})) E_a(y_{a,j}) + \psi_a(y_{a,j}) r_a(y_{a,j})] \frac{1}{\Phi_a(y_{a,j})} \right]}_{\text{terminal sampling events}} \\
& \times \underbrace{\left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{k=1}^{K_a} \psi_a(z_{a,k}) (1 - r_a(z_{a,k})) \frac{\Phi_a(z_{a,k})}{\Phi_a(z_{a,k})} \right]}_{\text{ancestral sampling events}} \\
& \times \underbrace{\left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{l=1}^{L_{a,b}} [\gamma_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l}) + \lambda_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l}) E_a(w_{a,b,l})] \frac{\Phi_b(w_{a,b,l})}{\Phi_a(w_{a,b,l})} \right]}_{\text{transition sampling events}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S18}$$

Step 5: Condition the Likelihood

We conclude, as in the single type model by multiplying the likelihood by including a general form of

conditioning \mathcal{S} .

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}(\Theta_{\text{MBDS}} | \mathcal{T}, \mathcal{C}) = & \mathcal{S} \times \left[\prod_{a=1}^A \rho_a^{N_a} \right] \times [\Phi_{c^*}(T)] \times \left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{b=1}^A \prod_{i=1}^{I_{a,b}} \lambda_{a,b}(x_{a,b,i}) \Phi_b(x_{a,b,i}) \right] \\
& \times \left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{j=1}^{J_a} [\psi_a(y_{a,j})(1 - r_a(y_{a,j}))E_a(y_{a,j}) + \psi_a(y_{a,j})r_a(y_{a,j})] \frac{1}{\Phi_a(y_{a,j})} \right] \\
& \times \left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{k=1}^{K_a} \psi_a(z_{a,k})(1 - r_a(z_{a,k})) \right] \\
& \times \left[\prod_{a=1}^A \prod_{b \neq a}^A \prod_{l=1}^{L_{a,b}} [\gamma_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l}) + \lambda_{a,b}(w_{a,b,l})E_a(w_{a,b,l})] \frac{\Phi_b(w_{a,b,l})}{\Phi_a(w_{a,b,l})} \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{S19}$$

Due to the combination of cladogenetic change and different possibility of hidden birth events due to extinction and sampling, there are six different types of birth events included in the likelihood of the sampled tree. The following diagram summarizes these different birth events and how each is included in the equation (S19).

Figure S1: The six possible birth events in the sampled tree and how each is included in the likelihood given by equation (S19).

S4 Tables

Variable	Definition
A	The number of discrete lineage types.
$\lambda_{a,\{b,c\}}(\tau)$	The time-varying rate at which lineage of type a gives rise to daughter lineages of type b and c at time τ .
$\mu_a(\tau)$	The time varying rate at which lineages of type a go extinct at time τ
$\psi_a(\tau)$	The time varying rate at which lineages of type a are sampled.
$r_a(\tau)$	The time varying probability that upon sampling lineages are removed.
$\gamma_{a,b}(\tau)$	The time varying rate at which lineages of type a transition to type b .
ρ_a	The probability a lineage of type a alive at the present day is sampled.
N_a	The number of lineages of type a sampled at the present day.
$\vec{x}_{a,b,c}$	A vector of length $I_{a,b}$ giving the timing of speciation events where a lineage of type a gives rise to a daughter of type b .
\vec{y}_a	A vector of length J_a giving the times at which lineages of type a are sampled for which there are no sampled descendants (sampled tips).
\vec{z}_a	A vector of length K_a giving the times at which lineages of type a are sampled for which there <i>are</i> sampled descendants (sampled ancestors).
$\vec{w}_{a,b}$	A vector of length $L_{a,b}$ giving the times at which lineages of type a mutate to lineages of type b .
c	The state at the origin (stem node) of the phylogeny.
\mathcal{T}	The tree topology.
\mathcal{C}	The colouring of the tree.
$g_e(a, \tau)$	The probability an edge e of type a alive at time τ gives rise to the subsequently observed phylogeny
$E_a(\tau)$	The probability a lineage of type a alive at time τ has no sampled descendants between time τ and the present day.
$\iota_{a,b}$	An indicator variable with value 2 if $a = b$ and 1 otherwise.
\mathcal{C}_y	The known tip states
\mathcal{C}_z	The known states of sampled ancestors
Θ_{MBDS}	The parameters of the multi-type BDS model
SSE Algorithm	
π_c	The probability the stem node has state c
$D_{N,a}(\tau)$	The probability a “topological” edge N of type a at time τ gives rise to the subsequently observed phylogeny.

Table S4: **Notation for the general multi-type model.** Throughout t represents time moving forward from the origin ($t = 0$) of the tree to the tips ($t = T$) and τ represents time moving backward from the tips ($\tau = 0$) to the origin ($\tau = T$). The indices a, b denote lineage types and can take on integer values between 1 and A .